

Review Article

Repositioning of the Agricultural Sector as the Only Criterion to Move Nigeria Forward

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Abstract

This paper takes a look at various successive regime policies and programmes of government and see how the Nigerian agriculture can be repositioned to achieve food security and restore the country back as a nation to be reckoned with her agricultural sector. More so, this paper look at the agricultural sector prior to independence when the nation enjoyed substantial success and development in the sector until the discovery of crude oil and government neglect of the agricultural sector due to substantial revenue from crude oil. The importance of the agricultural sector to the nation cannot be over emphasized. Apart from the fact that it has the potential to provide adequate food for the growing population, it also supply raw materials to a growing industrial sector. Over the years, the Nigerian government has injected money into the sector with various policies and programmes implemented in order to ensure that the country achieve food security. However, the sector has not been able to live up to its expectations due to myriad of problems that involve problems like bad governance, lack of financial support to farmers inadequate and untimely release of budgeted funds for agricultural development, use of crude farm tools, lack of storage facilities, general insecurity, farmers and herders crisis, climate change and other agro ecological hazards or disasters. In order to reposition the agricultural sector as the only criterion to move Nigeria forward, this paper highlighted several ways forward.

KEYWORDS: Agricultural sector, Nigeria, policies and food security.

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1. Introduction

Agriculture is the economic mainstay of the majority of the households in Nigeria and is a vital sector of the economy. The agricultural sector has a multiplier effect on any nation's socio-economic and industrial fabric because of the multifunctional nature of agriculture (Ogen, 2007). According to Ahmed (1993), agriculture is defined as the production of food and livestock and the purposeful tendering of plants and animals. Okolo (2004) described the agricultural sector as the most important sector of the Nigerian economy which holds a lot of potentials for the nation's future economic development as observed in the past. Notwithstanding the enviable position of the oil sector in the Nigerian economy over the past decades, the agricultural sector is arguably the most important sector of the economy. Emeka (2007) noted that the contribution of agriculture to the Gross Domestic product (GDP) has remained stable at a value that ranged between 30% and 42%. Agriculture also employs 65% of the labour force in Nigeria.

According to (<https://www.statista.com/statistics/115865/contribution-of-oil-sector-to-gdp-in-nigeria>), the agricultural sector of Nigeria between January and March 2021 contributed 22.35% of the nation's total GDP. More than 70% of Nigerians that are engaged in the agricultural sector are practicing it at subsistence level. Olajide et al. (2012) noted that the agricultural sector contributes a lot to the growth and development of an economy in four major ways, namely, food for man, factor contribution, market contribution and foreign exchange earnings. Olajide et al. (2012) observed that the agricultural sector is the largest sector in the Nigerian economy with its dominant share of the GDP, employing more than 70% of the labour force and generating about 88% of the non-oil foreign exchange earnings.

Despite its contribution to the economy, the agricultural sector of Nigeria faces a lot of challenges which has negative effect on its productivity. These include poor tenure system, low level of irrigation farming, climate change, land degradation, low technology, high production cost, poor distribution of inputs, limited financing, high post-harvest losses and poor access to markets. These challenges have silent agricultural productivity which is affecting the sector's contribution to the country's GDP as well as increasing food importation due to increase in population growth which is giving room for the declining levels of food sufficiency in the country. Though, the Nigerian government over the years have implemented several initiatives and programmes aimed at increasing agricultural productivity so as to provide sufficient quantities of food to meet domestic demand as well as abundance of commodity crops for export in the international market. Likewise these government initiatives and programmes also aimed at reversing forest loss and degradation, promote sustainable management of natural resources, rehabilitating degraded lands and reduce erosion and climate vulnerability.

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As a result of import substitution industrialization (ISI) strategy adopted by the government, various consumer goods which were previously imported were locally produced. Furthermore, measures like tariff and quota were put in place to protect and ensure that local industries were allowed to grow which led to job creation within a short time. Stronger productivity has kept prices stable within the economy. Unemployment rate was around 1.5% which largely involved primary and secondary school leavers (Akpan, 2012). The agricultural development was given priority attention during the colonial era which gave birth to various research institutes and extension services (Nwachukwu, 2006). In spite of Nigeria abundant agricultural resources coupled with oil wealth, poverty remains prevalent in the country and has grown out of control since the late 1990's. Over 90% of Nigerians are now classified as poor and 35% of them in absolute poverty (IFAD, 2011). Poverty is widely common the in rural areas where 80% of the population lives lower than the poverty line. Nigeria has an increasingly growing population of over 200 million people, growing at about 3% a year. Despite the demographic boom, roughly half of Nigerians are living in extreme poverty. What is worse is that hunger and malnutrition have been on the rise in the country since the collapse of oil prices in 2014.

Over the years, government continuous focus on oil as a major foreign exchange earner has led to neglect of agriculture. The growing population is now dependent on imported staples food, including but not limited to wheat, fish and rice which has led to constant rise of the food import bills (Nwajuiba, 2013). About 90% of Nigeria's food is produced by small scale farmers who cultivates small portion of land and depend on rainfall rather than irrigation. The productivity of rural population is hindered by government neglect of the agricultural sector which has failed food security thereby resulting to food insecurity in Nigeria. The smallholder farmers are constrained by many problems including those with poor access to modern inputs and credit, poor infrastructure, inadequate access to markets, land and environmental degradation, and inadequate research and extension services (Manyong et al., 2005).

The Nigerian agricultural system has the potential to replace the oil and gas sector owing to the fact that it is a major employer of skilled and unskilled labour and as a major contributor to Nigeria's per capita income and economic growth by reducing poverty and adjusting balance of payments deficits if and only if the agricultural sector can be transformed. In response to the dwindling performance of agriculture in the country, governments have, over the decades, initiated numerous policies and programmes aimed at restoring the agricultural sector to its pride of place in the economy. However, no significant success has been achieved due to the several persistent constraints inhibiting the performance of the sector (Manyong et al., 2005). Hence, this paper tends to discuss the need to reposition the agricultural sector of Nigeria due to the benefits it provides a growing economy.

2. NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL SECTOR AS AT TODAY

Nigeria has 70.8 million hectares of agricultural land area with maize, cassava, guinea corn, yam, beans, millet and rice being the major crops. Animal production has remained underexploited. Livestock mostly reared by farm families in Nigeria are the small ruminants like goats (76 million), sheep (43.4 million) and cattle (18.4 million). The ecology in the northern part of Nigeria makes it famous for livestock keeping. Poultry population stands at 180 million birds (<https://www.fao.org/nigeria/fao-in-nigeria/nigeria-at-a-glance/en/>).

Nigeria is the largest fish consumer in Africa and among the largest fish consumers in the world with about 3.2 million metric tons of fish consumed yearly. Nigeria's fisheries and aquaculture are among the fastest growing subsectors. With a coastline of 853 km and over 14 million hectares of inland waters, total fish production per year is close to 1 million metric tons (313,231 metric tons from aquaculture and 759,828 metric tons from fisheries). Fishing has been a vital livelihood for the poor as well as an important protein source at the household level in Nigeria. The aquaculture subsector is considered a very viable alternative to meeting the country's need for self-sufficiency in fish production and nutritional needs.

The contribution of the forestry subsector to agriculture and development in general cannot be overemphasized. According to (<https://www.fao.org/nigeria/fao-in-nigeria/nigeria-at-a-glance/en/>), Nigeria's forest ecosystems are threatened by rapid population growth and economic activities with annual deforestation rate ranging between 0.72% and 2.3%. The factors behind this trend just to mention a few include agricultural expansion, heavy reliance on firewood and charcoal energy, unsustainable timber extraction, urbanization, grazing, bush fires, infrastructure development etc.

3 AGRICULTURAL POLICIES AND PROGRAMMES PUT IN PLACE BY GOVERNMENT IN NIGERIA

3.1 From 1946 to 1956 Period

A number of agricultural policies have been formulated in Nigeria before and after independence. In the Colonial Ten Year Development Plan which spanned from 1946 to 1956, the commodity crop production emphasized upon were mainly oil palm, cocoa, rubber, cotton and groundnuts. The document contained very little or no proposal for increased food production. The need for active government intervention in the Agricultural sector through reform programmes was formed by the dearth and neglect of agriculture in Nigeria, due to the rising fortunes in crude oil in the early 1970's. Before then, Nigeria had a very robust agricultural sector with self-sufficiency in food production and minimal imports of processed food for the elites; farmers produced enough food crops to feed the population and foreign exchange receipts from exported crops was used to finance government expenditure in education,

health, construction and finance, etc. The northern region (including the middle belt) was largely exporting cotton, hides and groundnuts; the South West region specialized in cocoa, while the South East region (including the present South-South region) was a major exporter of rubber and palm produce. Government focused on research, extension services, marketing and pricing of export crops (Ojeka et al., 2016).

3.2 Between 1962 and 1968 Period

Between 1962 and 1968, the first National Development Plan on agriculture was created to increase the production of export crops through better seed distribution and more modern methods of cultivation. Farm settlements and cooperative plantations as well as Tractor Hiring Units were established and agricultural extension services were greatly expanded (Asoegwu and Asoegwu, 2007). This Plan Period was a success as cash crops accounted for about 80% of total export and 45% of the GDP. However, food sector was not mentioned in this that had 11.6% capital allocation by both Federal and State Governments to Agriculture (Osakwe and Ojo, 1986).

3.3 From 1970 – 1974 Period

From 1970 – 1974, the Second National Development Plan was formed during which the National Agricultural and Cooperative Bank (NACB) was established in 1973 to facilitate agricultural financing to farmers. Also, the National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP) was initiated which laid emphasis on agricultural research and extension support to farmers. However, with massive exploration of crude oil which contributed over 98% to total export and 73% of GDP, the agricultural policies and programs were clumsily executed and virtually abandoned by succeeding military regimes (Opara, 2006). Consequently, capital allocated to agriculture for crop production, irrigation, research, credit (loans or subsidy), mechanization, man-power and agricultural extension services, declined (Osakwe and Ojo, 1986). For instance, the cocoa plantations suffered serious setback, the cotton and groundnut pyramids disappeared, hides and skin became food for the embattled Nigerian populace, and the oil palm plantations were battle fields during the Biafra/Nigeria. Asoegwu and Asoegwu (2007) observed that the civil war died a natural death due to neglect. The disaster on agriculture and food production was enormous and the effect on Nigerians has not been ameliorated till date.

3.4 From 1975 – 1980 Period

From 1975 – 1980, the Third National development Plan focused on food production because there was obvious decline in national food supplies due to poorly executed or neglected past agricultural policies and the effects of the civil war. The oil boom caused massive rural-to-urban drift made up mainly of the younger generation. Several crop farms suffered “death” because of inadequate or zero maintenance and there was serious deficit in food production (Alatise, 2001). In 1976, the Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) programme was launched. The programme focused on

building the spirit of dignity of labor and reengaging the idle hands back to land. In the same year, Marketing Boards were abolished. Production and Marketing Companies were established such as National Grain Production Company for food grains and National Root Crop Production Company for root crops. Other policy and strategic measures taken by Government during this period were the establishment of River Basin Development Authorities (RBDAs), National Seed Multiplication Scheme, Agro-Service Centers, Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs). The Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) was also established to provide agricultural finance. Many research and tertiary institutions were established to formulate and implement research programmes aimed at improving agricultural food production. Even with all these policies, the total capital allocation to agriculture by both Federal and State Governments further declined to 7.1% (Asoegwu and Asoegwu, 2007). This goes further to show that Government was not supporting the agricultural sector with adequate financial backing for proper execution of the programme.

3.5 From 1981 – 1985 Period

From 1981 – 1985, the Fourth National Development Plan saw the emergence of the Green Revolution which tried to give more powers and impetus to the River Basin Development Authorities and the ADPs to produce more food for the nation with more capital allocated to the agricultural sector (Osakwe and Ojo, 1986). Even though these efforts seemed to have been guided by genuine concerns, they failed to make the necessary impacts in the agricultural sector because of fundamental structural problems in the economy. According to Asoegwu and Asoegwu (2007), the agricultural sector contribution to GDP declined by about 20% during the period. This resulted in increased shortage of food as evidenced by increased food imports and increased high prices. Igbeka (2003) noted that the experience gathered from the three National Plan Periods convinced Government that there cannot be no alternative to well-designed and articulated agricultural policies as instruments for promoting agricultural growth and development in Nigeria.

3.6 Other Intervention of Government

In 1988, the Federal Government published the first ever agricultural policy document for Nigeria aimed at redressing the underdevelopment of agriculture, streamlining policies in all tiers of government and ensuring policy stability (Opara, 2006). However, many factors worked against the implementation of this policy. They include poor funding and poor state of infrastructure; poor administration of government support to agriculture and abandonment of projects midstream due to political reasons; lack of appropriate technology to reduce drudgery in agricultural production and processing and inadequate availability of inputs such as improved seeds and breed stock among others (Asoegwu and Asoegwu, 2007).

In the periods between 1992 and 1998, succeeding governments saw that women involvement in agriculture was high and as such government policies were centered on women. Programme such as Better Life for Rural Women; Family Support Program (FSP); Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP) were initiated. These were meant to empower the women for more and better involvement in agriculture and other rural activities in order to enhance the production of food and agricultural raw materials.

From 1999 till date, the various governments have implemented different reform programmes ranging from privatization, commercialization, deregulation to corruption and financial crimes. These are meant to stabilize the economy and make it more productive ensuring that the era of subsidies and over-protection of key sectors of the economy including agriculture is over (Van Otterdijk, 2005). In 2001, a new Agricultural Policy was introduced and in order to fast track the gains of the policy, government set up Presidential Initiatives in Agriculture (PIA) in 2004 and the National Special Food Security Program (NSFSP) and FADAMA II in 2005. NSFSP and FADAMA I, II and III, were all targeted at raising agricultural productivity and production, food security and eliminate poverty among poor rural farmers.

In 2006, the National Agricultural Development Fund was established with the aim of addressing the problem of inadequate funding of agriculture on a sustainable basis. The above policies necessitated the New Economic Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) as well as the Lagos Plan of Action (LPA) to acknowledge that agricultural mechanization and environmental stability are a *sine qua non* for increased food production and food security (Faborode, 2005). The administration signed the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP) of NEPAD Protocol. This Protocol focuses on investment into (i) extending the area under sustainable land management and reliable water control systems; (ii) improving rural infrastructure and market access; and (iii) increasing food supply and reducing hunger. In spite of the various agricultural programmes and policies initiated by different administrations for the development of Agriculture in Nigeria, there has not been any significant growth in agricultural output since the 1970s. Agriculture's contribution to the non-oil GDP was stable at about 40 per cent in recent years.

Around the time of 2010 to 2011, the Government of Nigeria, after years of relegating agricultural sector, began to reform the sector. The Government implemented a new strategy, called the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA). From 2011 to 2016, the focus was on rebuilding a sector whose relevance had shrunk dramatically. That was reflected in the lack of lending to farmers by the financial system and the dramatic levels of food imports from across the world (FMARD, 2016).

The policy document of President Jonathan's administration in relation to the transformation agenda is to develop and reposition the agricultural sector of Nigeria as this focuses on seven core areas of reformation which include:

- i) Elimination of all forms of corruption in fertilizer and seed distribution by ensuring that such key farm inputs are sold directly to genuine farmers at approved rates to prevent diversion and exploitation.
- ii) Growth Enhancement Support (GES) scheme by which E-Wallet was developed for input delivery to farmers.
- iii) Revolution in Food Crops and Grains, especially the rice reform programme that had led to establishment of 13 new Rice Mills with two million metric tons per year production capacity, the development of cassava value chains with the establishment of two large scale cassava processing plants through the support of 6 billion US € 6 billion investment commitment from a large US investor for the production of ethanol as well as sorghum transformation to boost output to reach over two million metric tons per year (Raji, 2013).
- iv) Cash Crop Production Reform, especially Cocoa Transformation Agenda with target output of 500,000 metric tons by 2018 through sustainable production systems by maintenance of existing farms, rehabilitation of old plantations, and expansion programmes through intensification and good agricultural practices. This is aimed at creating 400,000 jobs for Nigerian cocoa sub-sector and increasing cocoa processing capacity of factories, transforming cotton production sub-sector to raise output from 125,000 metric tons of seed cotton in 2011 to 500,000 metric tons in 2015, and also raising international export capacity from 22,500 tons in 2011/2012 to 170,000 by 2015 (The Presidency, 2013).
- v) Attraction of private investor to the agricultural sector with over US€8 billion of private sector investment commitments was already deployed in agribusiness ventures, and attraction of large indigenous and global multinational firms like Flour Mills of Nigeria, Dangote Group, Syngenta, Indorama, AGCO and Belster into agricultural sector promotion and development (Raji, 2013).
- vi) Institutional Reforms whereby the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development has been decentralized with the appointment of State and Regional Directors.
- vii) Attraction of fund from International Agencies to develop agricultural sector and this has led to the mobilization of over US€4 billion from World Bank, IFAD, China-EXIM, Melinda Gates Foundations, DFID, ADB and the Ford Foundation to support Nigeria's transformation programme in the agricultural sector (The Presidency, 2013).

The Buhari led Administration brought in several agricultural programmes which include the following:

- i. Anchor Borrowers Programme: This programme was established by CBN and was launched by the President in November 2015. It was intended to create a linkage between anchor companies involved in the processing and small holders' farmers of the key agricultural commodities. The Anchor Borrowers Programme provides farmers' inputs in kind and cash to small holders farmers to boost production. At harvest the small holders farmers supplies their produce to the Anchor who pays the cash equivalent to the farmers account.
- ii. Presidential Fertilizer Initiative (PFI): It was launched in December 2016 as a result of a partnership between government of Nigeria and Morocco. It was implemented as a public private partnership in Nigeria, led by the Nigerian Sovereign Investment Authority (NSIA) and the Fertilizer Producers and Suppliers Association of Nigeria (FEPSAN).
- iii. Youth Farm Lab: This was an initiative of the Federal Ministry of Agriculture in conjunction with synergas, to train Nigerian youths in livestock production and sustainable urban agriculture. It seeks Nigerians between the ages of 18 and 35 years who are passionate about agriculture and believe in its profitability potentials.
- iv. Presidential Economic Diversification Initiative: It was launched in July 2017 to support the revival of moribund industries especially Agro processing by facilitating new investments, reducing regulatory bottlenecks and enabling access to credit. This initiative has made breakthrough in the Agri-business sector in Imo and Ondo States.
- v. Food Security Council: It was launched in March 2018 by the President. The broad objectives of the Council include:
 - a) Developing sustainable solutions to farmers-herdsmen clashes.
 - b) Climate change and desertification and their impact on farmland, grazing areas and lakes, rivers and other water bodies.
 - c) Oil spillage and its impact on Niger Delta fishing communities.
 - d) Piracy and banditry.
 - e) Agricultural research institutions and extension services.
 - f) Problems of smuggling.
 - g) The Council will also take interest in regional and global policies and trends that bear implications for food security in Nigeria.

Therefore, in order to reposition the agricultural sector and to also make this country a food security nation, her policy on agriculture should be reformed and made stable.

4. IMPORTANCE OF AGRICULTURAL SECTOR TO THE DEVELOPED NATION

The benefits of the agricultural sector to this nation's economy were discussed under the following subsections.

4.1 Source of Food Supply

Agriculture provides the basic source of food for human and animal consumption, No matter the level of development, all countries in the world need food to feed her growing population and also to survive.

4.2 Contribution to National Income and Economic Growth

Most income generated from agricultural produce exported to foreign countries contribute and boost the national income of the country. Foreign exchange generated from exported agricultural produce gives the country economic stability. The agricultural sector provides employment opportunities for the teeming population, export revenue earnings and eradicate poverty in the country.

4.3 Sources of Raw Material for Industries

The agricultural sector plays a very important role in any growing economy. Apart from providing food, it also provide the necessary raw material for industries. Most agro allied industries are beneficiary of raw materials needed for production.

4.4 Source of Foreign Exchange for the Country

Most of the developing countries of the world relied on export of agricultural cash crops to generate enough foreign exchange for economic development. Nigeria, prior to discovery of oil, agriculture serves as a major foreign exchange earner for the development of the nation. The former three geopolitical regions were developed through foreign exchange earn from agriculture.

4.5 Employment Opportunities for Rural People

Before the discovery of oil, agriculture was the mainstay of this nation's economy which provides employment opportunities for the rural populace thereby stemming rural - urban migration. About 70% of Nigerian populace were gainfully engaged in agricultural production, both at subsistence and commercial scale levels.

4.6 Improving Rural Welfare

Rural participation in agricultural production aside from providing means of sustenance, most rural farmers engaged in cash crop production through agricultural board which by so doing generated more income, improve the lives of the rural farmers and therefore reducing poverty among them. The participation of rural dwellers in agriculture provide an avenue for government to provide basic, social, health and economic infrastructure due to their contribution to the economy.

Infrastructure such as good roads, electricity, primary and secondary health centres and agricultural extension services were provided.

5. DIFFICULTIES DEBARING THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF NIGERIA FROM MOVING FORWARD

There are several difficulties debarring this nation's agricultural sector from moving forward. These difficulties are discussed under the following subsections.

5.1 Lack of Financial Resources

The country today is suffering from a very serious food shortage due to lack of financial support in encouraging those who are desirous TO engage IN agriculture as a means of livelihood. Administrative bottlenecks and delay in getting loans from financial institutions are impediments to the growth of the sector.

5.2 Illiteracy

Majority of Nigerians engaged in agriculture are the rural farmers and many of them are illiterates and unaware of the modern practices involved in agriculture today. The local farmers' inability to read and write has been a major setback to the various efforts channeled towards ensuring food production in Nigeria.

5.3 Use of Manual and Crude Farm Tools and Techniques

Most local farmers lack the financial means to procure or rent modern agricultural machinery and farm tools for use in agricultural production. The use of outdated farm tools and techniques act as a setback in agricultural food production outputs of the country.

5.4 Lack of Social Amenities

A large number of rural dwellers engaged in farming lack good social amenities. Among the social amenities involved just to mention a few include access to good roads in transporting finished cultivated agricultural produce and lack of water for irrigation and electricity. All these hampers on the farmer's drive to contribute to the economic growth through agricultural production.

5.5 Lack of Food Storage and Processing Facilities

Due to lack of adequate storage facilities, a large number of perishable farm produces end up damaged or wasted before they get to the final consumers of the farm produce. A substantial part of the farm produce is lost between the farm and the consumer. These losses are commonly found in perishable farm produce such as vegetables and animal products. In view of this, adequate and effective infrastructure for storage, processing and transportation activities of these farm produce must be put in place to enhance productivity.

5.6 Lack of Scientific and Technological Know-how

Today, agricultural practice has moved to an advanced scientific technique stage to boost food production. Advance technological research into modern ways of achieving higher yield of agricultural produce is lacking in the country. For Nigeria to experience higher yield in food crops and animal production we must move with the trend. Efforts should be geared towards more advanced scientific method of production. Our schools should focus more on practical than theory in the agricultural educational curriculum meant to boost and increase food production.

5.7 Global Warming and Ecological Problems

Gas flaring and chemical emission into the atmosphere is causing global warming and other ecological damage. Today, the world is experiencing more rains and flooding which have accounted for farmers loses in their farmlands. This year, Nigeria experienced major flooding in 18 States of the federation causing damage to farmlands and preventing little harvested crops from being transported which have led to the huge increase in the prices of farm produce. Also, persistence drought in the northern belt of the country is a major problem in food production. Multinational companies are being encouraged to embrace alternative to fossil fuel to reduce gas emission to avoid global warming.

5.8 Decline in the Quality of Farmers

In Nigeria the large bulk of people engaged in farming are the rural dwellers with most of them comprising of the aged farmers with no sign of replacement coming from our youth in showing interest in taking up farming as a means of livelihood. The youth are no longer interested in farming or agriculture related job because they consider it to be a job for the poor or less privileged. Most youth who should have engaged in agriculture are migrating to the cities to search for better jobs.

5.9 Land Tenure System

The Nigeria land tenure system even though it places land ownership on families, government seizure of large parcel of arable land through government fiat and laws without recourse to the family whose land are forcefully taken hindered the use of such arable land for agricultural purposes. The Nigeria land tenure system leaves the farmers with little uneconomical small fragmented land for farming. This situation impedes improvement in the increase of food production. The land use Decree of 1978 was meant to solve this problem but up till date it has achieved little or nothing towards this direction.

5.10 Inadequate Staffing of Experienced Extension Workers

The lack of engaging experienced extension workers on the field and the shortfall in their personnel is one of the major constraints confronting agricultural development in Nigeria.

5.11 Poor Government Policies and Planning

Over the years, successive government in a bid to outshine predecessors comes up with different agricultural policies which neglects the existing policy thereby creating a vacuum in policy implementation. Policies churned out are expected to be tailored to aid agriculture and economic boom rather because of miss match of policy, economic gloom is the order of the day by various successive governments. The resultant effect of these poor policies and planning is low growth rate, high unemployment rate as well as increase in price of goods and services.

5.12 Neglect of the Agricultural Sector and Over Dependence on Oil

Prior to independence, agriculture played a greater role in Nigeria economic prosperity witnessed before the discovery of oil. The discovery of large quantity of oil had led to the neglect and abandoning of agriculture and other sources of revenue making Nigeria economy a mono-economy. Today, Nigeria imports those agricultural produce she hitherto produce. For Nigeria to be food sufficient, concerted efforts should be made to diversify the economy so that every sector will contribute her quota and be productive.

5.13 Farmers/herdsmen Conflict

The nefarious activities of killer herdsmen in almost every part of Nigeria have negatively affected farming activities thereby giving room for less productivity in agriculture. Farmers are being harm bushed, chased, maimed and killed in their farms with impunity to no end despite government's effort to stem the killings of these innocent farmers. Farmers are afraid to go to farms as herdsmen invade farmland and destroy farm produce such as cassava and grain crops which falls under the important staple food of most Nigerians. This situation has led to the sudden increase in the prices of food stuff and the present cause undue hardship melted upon the populace

6. WAYS FORWARD

The repositioning of the agricultural sector of Nigeria is the only way out to ensure adequate provision of food for her teeming and growing population. In order to reposition this nation's agricultural sector to perform its important roles toward national development, the following were recommended as ways forward which were discussed under the following subsections,

6.1 Funding of Research for National Development

Research institutes should be properly funded to develop and improve innovations to boost agricultural practices.

6.2 Promotion of Mechanized Farming

Mechanization is crucial for self-sufficiency in food production worldwide. Modern farming machines and inputs should be made cheap, available and accessible.

6.3 Provision of Storage Facilities

Most farm produce are perishable in nature which needs adequate storage facilities in preserving them. As a result of this, government should provide modern silos and warehouses that can withstand adverse weather and prevent spoilage of farm produce.

6.4 Growing of Crops consumed on Commercial Scale Level

This is the time Nigeria should start growing the crops she produces at commercial scale level for domestic consumption and export purpose to other African countries and to the rest of the world.

6.5 Adequate Provision of Capital

Government should provide farmers with enough capital mainly for agricultural purposes. Credit facilities should be made available through agricultural banks set up for the promotion of the agricultural sector such as Nigerian Agricultural Development and Cooperative Bank and as well as the Bank of Industry. There is need to closely monitor these lending banks in order to ensure that the credit facilities extended to farmers are not diverted but carefully used for the purpose it was intended for. Loans issued at minimal interest rate should be given to farmers which for this reason government should give directive to Deposit Money Banks (DMB) otherwise known as commercial banks to put aside certain percentage of their capital for lending to farmers at a minimal interest rate.

6.6 Rehabilitation of Nigeria's Irrigation Infrastructure

Irrigation facilities are available particularly in the northern part of the country but needs rehabilitation to be effective.

6.7 Restoration of the Growth Enhancement Scheme

The scheme was introduced during the administration of President Goodluck Ebele Jonathan and should be restored because it is critical in the crop commodity value chain. The uniqueness of the scheme has enable farmers to have direct access to input, which is critical to boost food production. The scheme enables farmers to get fertilizers because there was a platform created whereby the data of all farmers were captured.

6.8 Reviving Agricultural Settlements

Government should revive all agricultural settlements in the country. Youths could be deployed to use agricultural settlements for farming as this would increase food production to achieve food security.

6.9 Subsidize Inputs to Farmers

Subsidize inputs to farmers is very important at this period. There will be a time when farmers will no longer demand for support, but at present it is critical to empower Nigerian farmers to be independent of government interventions.

6.10 Large Scale Farming

A large number of Nigerian farmers practice subsistence agriculture which alone hinders the country from in achieving food security. Therefore, for agriculture to aid gross domestic product and prevent food insecurity, rural farmers must engage in large scale farming. This will boost the quantity of agricultural output for export which in the long run give more foreign exchange earnings for the nation.

6.11 Agricultural Extension Service

The Agricultural Extension department should assist farmers in the area of advising them on how to get better yield for their crops and also offering periodic education on modern approach to agriculture.

6.12 Government compliance of the Malabo Agreement

Concerted effort should be made by the government to comply with the Malabo agreement declaration and commitments which state that 10% of national annual budget should be earmarked for agriculture, in addition to this, there should be urgent need for massive and unprecedented investment in the agricultural sector for domestic consumption, rural infrastructural development and export promotion.

7. Conclusion

This paper has extensively dealt on how the agricultural sector can be repositioned for Nigeria to achieve food security. The study highlight the difficulties faced and suggested the ways forward in moving the agricultural sector of Nigeria forward. The study noted that various policies and programmes of government have laudable and good intentions but failed at implementation stage. The government should give agriculture the attention it deserves at the moment for the economic growth of the country. Urgent need must be made for massive investment in the agricultural sector so as to provide for more domestic consumption, rural infrastructural development and export promotion. The government should avoid policy inconsistency, remove bottlenecks in granting credit facilities to farmers. In order to ensure adequate funding of the sector, concerted effort and determination should be made by the government to adhere strictly to the agreement reached at the African agricultural forum at Maputo/ Malabo declaration which stipulate that 10% of the national annual budget should be allocated for agricultural development.

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